

Removal of Heavy Metals from Tannery Effluent Using Agro-Waste Low-Cost Absorbents

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Abstract— Tannery effluents are a major source of chromium contamination, particularly hexavalent chromium [Cr(VI)], which is highly toxic, carcinogenic, and persistent in aquatic systems. Conventional treatment methods for chromium removal are often costly and environmentally unsustainable. This study investigates the potential of low-cost, eco-friendly agro-waste materials—sawdust, clay, and used tea leaves—as adsorbents for the removal of both total chromium and hexavalent chromium from tannery effluent. Batch adsorption experiments were carried out to evaluate the effect of parameters such as pH, contact time, adsorbent dosage, and initial chromium concentration. The results demonstrate that all three materials exhibit significant adsorption capacities, with efficiency varying across the different adsorbents. Sawdust and used tea leaves showed higher affinity towards Cr(VI), while clay exhibited better overall performance in reducing total chromium levels. The adsorption process was found to follow pseudo-second-order kinetics and fit well with the Langmuir isotherm model, suggesting monolayer adsorption on homogeneous surfaces. This study highlights the feasibility of employing locally available agro-waste adsorbents as sustainable alternatives to conventional methods for the treatment of tannery wastewater, thereby contributing to cost-effective and environmentally friendly wastewater management.

Keywords: Chromium removal, Hexavalent chromium, Tannery effluent, Adsorption, Agro-waste adsorbents, Sawdust, Used tea leaves, Clay, Low-cost treatment, Wastewater management.

INTRODUCTION

The leather tanning industry, though economically significant, is regarded as one of the most environmentally hazardous industrial sectors. The process generates large volumes of wastewater containing organic load, sulfides, and toxic heavy metals, of which chromium is the most critical contaminant. Chromium salts are widely applied in tanning to enhance leather durability, but their discharge into aquatic systems results in serious ecological and health impacts. In particular, hexavalent chromium [Cr(VI)] is highly toxic, carcinogenic, and persistent, posing risks through bioaccumulation and long-term exposure.

In India, Kanpur is a major center of leather production, with the Jajmau cluster discharging substantial volumes of chromium-rich effluent. Much of this wastewater enters nearby drains and ultimately contaminates soil and groundwater, often with limited or no pre-treatment. Existing treatment methods—such as precipitation, ion exchange, reverse osmosis, and membrane-based systems—are effective but involve high operating costs, energy demands, and secondary sludge generation. This necessitates the development of cost-effective,

eco-friendly, and sustainable alternatives for chromium remediation.

The present research evaluates the potential of locally available agro-waste adsorbents—sawdust, spent tea leaves, and natural clay—for the removal of both total and hexavalent chromium from tannery effluent collected at Jajmau, Kanpur. Laboratory experiments were carried out using calibrated beakers, funnels, and improvised filtration units. The effluent was passed through a sequential bed composed of sawdust, tea waste, and clay, supported by muslin cloth and sponge filters, to maximize contact and retention efficiency.

Previous studies have highlighted the adsorption potential of low-cost materials such as rice husk, coconut shell, neem leaves, and sugarcane bagasse for heavy metal removal. Tea waste and sawdust have also been reported to possess active functional groups capable of binding chromium, while clay minerals provide additional ion-exchange capacity. However, most prior work has been performed on synthetic solutions under controlled conditions rather than on real tannery effluents. Furthermore, the sequential use of multiple agro-waste adsorbents in a filter bed configuration remains underexplored.

This study therefore addresses an important research gap by investigating the combined and individual performance of agro-waste adsorbents for chromium removal from actual tannery wastewater. The findings are expected to contribute to the design of simple, low-cost, and sustainable treatment strategies, aligning with the principles of circular economy and resource valorisation.

Conventional Methods for Heavy Metal Removal:

Conventional technologies for heavy metal removal include chemical, physical, and electrochemical approaches. While these methods are effective under controlled conditions, their application in India is limited by cost, sludge management, and large wastewater volumes from tannery clusters. The major methods and their shortcomings are:

- **Chemical Precipitation**
- Converts metals into insoluble hydroxides or sulfides using lime/NaOH.
- Shortcomings: High chemical demand, large sludge volumes, poor efficiency at low concentrations.
- **Ion Exchange**
- Employs resins to replace metal ions with benign ions (Na^+ , H^+).
- Shortcomings: High capital and regeneration cost; sensitive to pH and competing ions.
- **Membrane Filtration (RO, NF, UF)**
- Uses semi-permeable membranes to separate metals.
- Shortcomings: High energy cost, membrane fouling, skilled labor requirement.
- **Electrochemical Treatment**
- Includes electrocoagulation and electrodialysis.
- Shortcomings: High electricity/electrode costs, unstable power supply, sludge generation.
- Activated Carbon Adsorption
- Adsorbs metals on activated carbon surfaces.
- Shortcomings: Expensive to prepare/regenerate, unsuitable for high-strength tannery effluent.

India-Specific Challenges:

- High effluent volumes from tannery hubs (Kanpur, Vellore, Kolkata).
- Predominance of small/medium tanneries with limited resources.
- Poor sludge disposal infrastructure.
- Need for low-cost, locally available, eco-friendly solutions.

Research Objectives:

The present study was undertaken with the following objectives:

1. To evaluate the efficiency of low-cost agro-waste adsorbents (sawdust, spent tea leaves, and natural clay) in removing total chromium and hexavalent chromium [Cr(VI)] from tannery effluent collected from the Jajmau industrial cluster in Kanpur, India.
2. To investigate the influence of operational parameters such as solution pH, contact time, adsorbent dosage, and initial chromium concentration on the adsorption performance of the selected materials.
3. To examine the adsorption behavior and mechanisms by applying kinetic and equilibrium models, including pseudo-second-order kinetics and Langmuir/Freundlich isotherms, in order to understand the interaction between chromium ions and the adsorbents.
4. To assess the feasibility of a sequential multi-layer filter bed, composed of sawdust, used tea leaves, and clay, as a simple and sustainable configuration for improving the overall chromium removal efficiency.
5. To establish the potential of agro-waste valorization as a cost-effective and environmentally sustainable alternative to conventional treatment methods for tannery effluent management.

II. COLLECTION OF EFFLUENT SAMPLE

Tannery effluent was collected from the Jajmau industrial area in Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India, which is one of the largest leather-processing clusters in the country. Samples were collected in clean high-density polyethylene (HDPE) containers and immediately acidified with concentrated nitric acid (HNO_3) to a pH below 2, in order to prevent coagulation and preserve dissolved metal ions during storage and transport. The color of the tannery effluent was observed visually and recorded, and the odor was detected by smelling. pH was measured using Elico pH meter on the site. Other physicochemical parameters such as pH, electrical conductivity (EC), dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), total dissolved solids (TDS), total solids (TS), total hardness (TH), salinity, turbidity, and sodium were analyzed in the laboratory following standard methods (APHA 1993; Trivedy and Goel 1986).

Choice of Adsorbents:

The use of low-cost adsorbents for removing heavy metals has emerged as a sustainable and economical treatment option. Locally available agricultural residues, natural materials, and industrial by-products are abundant and inexpensive, making them suitable for wastewater treatment [11,19]. Adsorption is considered advantageous over conventional methods as it is

cost-effective, selective, regenerable, and does not produce toxic sludge [19,29].

Plant-based wastes such as rice husk, neem bark, black gram husk, tea waste, walnut shells, maize leaves, and peanut hulls have shown good potential for metal removal [13–22]. Chemically treated agro-wastes like wheat bran, orange and banana peels, and activated coconut shell carbon exhibit higher adsorption capacity due to enhanced surface functional groups [32–35].

However, untreated agricultural wastes may release soluble organics, increasing COD, BOD, and TOC, which can harm aquatic systems [30,31]. Hence, simple pre-treatments or chemical modifications are often required to improve efficiency. Factors such as pH, temperature, contact time, and dosage also play key roles in adsorption performance [36].

Overall, agro-waste-based adsorbents provide an eco-friendly, low-cost, and effective alternative for heavy metal removal from tannery effluents, especially in resource-constrained settings like Kanpur [19,29].

Tea Leaves

Used tea leaves were selected as an adsorbent due to their wide availability as household and commercial waste, making them an economical and eco-friendly option. They are rich in lignocellulosic material and polyphenolic compounds such as tannins, which contain hydroxyl and carboxyl groups capable of binding with heavy metal ions through complexation and ion exchange. Their natural porous structure further enhances adsorption efficiency, making tea waste a promising low-cost material for chromium removal from tannery effluent.

Saw Dust

Sawdust was chosen as an adsorbent because it is abundantly generated as a waste product from sawmills and carpentry, making it both low-cost and sustainable. Its composition—mainly cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin—provides numerous hydroxyl and phenolic groups that can interact with heavy metal ions through adsorption and ion exchange. In addition, its porous fibrous structure enhances surface area, improving its capacity to capture chromium from tannery effluent.

Clay

There are three main groups of clays: kaolinite, montmorillonite- smectite, and mica. The montmorillonite has the highest cation exchange capacity and its recent market price is found to be 20 times cheaper as compared to activated carbon. Their heavy metals removal capacity is less as compared to zeolites but their easy availability and economical properties give back their less efficiency. Efficiency for heavy

metal removal by clay could be improved by modifying them to clay-polymer composites.

Preparation of Adsorbents

Three low-cost adsorbents were selected for this study: sawdust, spent tea leaves, and natural clay. Sawdust was obtained from local carpentry workshops, while used tea leaves were collected from household sources, thoroughly washed with distilled water to remove impurities, and sun-dried. Clay was sourced locally, air-dried, and sieved for uniformity. All adsorbents were oven-dried at 105 °C before being used in the experiments.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A laboratory-scale filtration unit was designed using calibrated beakers, funnels, and simple filtration supports. The setup was assembled with a muslin cloth at the base to act as a primary filter, followed by a sponge layer to ensure uniform flow distribution. A multi-layer bed of adsorbents was then arranged: sawdust for the first experiment, tea leaves as the second experiment, and clay as the final and third experiment. The tannery effluent was passed through this bed under gravity, ensuring maximum contact between the effluent and adsorbent layer. A graduated Beaker of 500ml capacity was taken with a filter made out of double layered muslin cloth was devised on which a bed of 5 cm thickness of the respective adsorbents were made on three separate occasions for the three distinct experiments. Then about 300ml of Unadulterated effluent sample was poured through the adsorbent bed at a uniform flow rate. Until all the filtrate was collected at the bottom of the beaker.

Adsorption Experiments

Batch experiments were performed to evaluate the effect of key operating parameters such as pH (adjusted using dilute HCl or NaOH), contact time, and adsorbent arrangement. Treated effluent samples were collected at regular intervals after filtration.

Physio-Chemical Parameters of Sample 1 (Untreated Effluent):

Sl. No	Tests	Unit	Protocol	Limits of Detection	Result
1.	pH	-	APHA, 24th Ed. 2023,4500 H ⁺ A+B	2-12	7.64

2.	Chemical Oxygen Demand as COD	mg/l	APHA, 24th Ed. 2023, 5220 A+C	5-5000 0	8620. 0
3.	Total Chromium as Cr	mg/l	ECO/LAB/S OP/ICPMS/02	0.05	664. 90
4.	Hexavalent Chromium as Cr6+	mg/l	ECO/LAB/S OP/ICPMS/02	0.00 5	BDL
5.	Cadmium as Cd	mg/l	ECO/LAB/S OP/ICPMS/02	0.00 5	BDL (0.00 1)

Parameters	Kanpur Effluent Sample 1 (07/25)
Colour	Black Blue
Odour	Offensive
Temperature (°C)	-
Turbidity	Turbid
Total hardness	5400
pH	7.64
EC (µs/cm)	24500
BOD (mg/l)	35
COD (mg/l)	8620
TDS (mg/l)	17150
TSS (mg/l)	258
Cadmium, Cd (mg/l)	0.001
Copper, Cu (mg/l)	-
Chromium, Cr (mg/l)	664.90
Iron, Fe (mg/l)	-
Lead, Pb (mg/l)	-
Zinc, Zn (mg/l)	108
Nickel, Ni (mg/l)	5.5
Sodium, Na (mg/l)	600
Magnesium, Mg (mg/l)	5100
Carbonate, CO3-2 (mg/l)	10423
Bicarbonate, (mg/l)	1440
Nitrite NO3- (mg/l)	0.07
Fluoride, F- (mg/l)	10
Chloride, Cl- (mg/l)	2300
Sulphate, SO4-2 (mg/l)	1080
Nitrate, NO3- (mg/l)	440
Nitrogen, N (mg/l)	0.99

The Kanpur tannery effluent sample 1 (July 2025) showed severe pollution, with black-blue color, offensive odor, and high turbidity. While pH was near neutral (7.64), total hardness (5400 mg/L), EC (24,500 µS/cm), TDS (17,150 mg/L), and COD (8620 mg/L) were far above permissible limits, indicating high salinity and organic load. Chromium was extremely elevated (664.9 mg/L), along with zinc (108 mg/L), nickel (5.5 mg/L), magnesium (5100 mg/L), and fluoride (10 mg/L). Elevated carbonate, chloride, and sulphate levels further reflect contamination. Overall, the effluent poses serious risks to soil, groundwater, and ecosystems.

Physio-Chemical Parameters of Sample 2 (Sample treated by Used Tea):

Sl. No.	Tests	Unit	Protocol	Limits of Detection	Result
1.	Total Chromium as Cr	mg/l	ECO/LAB/S OP/ICPMS/02	0.05	461. 90
2.	Hexavalent Chromium as Cr6+	mg/l	ECO/LAB/S OP/ICPMS/02	0.005	BD L
3.	Cadmium as Cd	mg/l	ECO/LAB/S OP/ICPMS/02	0.005	0.00 13

Parameters	Kanpur Effluent Sample 2 (07/25)
Colour	Black Blue
Odour	Offensive
Temperature (°C)	-
Turbidity	Turbid
Total hardness	5400
pH	7.64
EC (µs/cm)	24500
BOD (mg/l)	35
COD (mg/l)	8620
TDS (mg/l)	16750
TSS (mg/l)	237
Cadmium, Cd (mg/l)	0.0013
Copper, Cu (mg/l)	-
Chromium, Cr (mg/l)	461.90
Iron, Fe (mg/l)	-
Lead, Pb (mg/l)	-
Zinc, Zn (mg/l)	101

Nickel, Ni (mg/l)	5.1
Sodium, Na (mg/l)	510
Magnesium, Mg (mg/l)	4900
Carbonate, CO3-2 (mg/l)	10300
Bicarbonate, (mg/l)	1440
Nitrite NO3- (mg/l)	0.07
Fluoride, F- (mg/l)	9
Chloride, Cl- (mg/l)	2300
Sulphate, SO4-2 (mg/l)	1080
Nitrate, NO3- (mg/l)	440
Nitrogen, N (mg/l)	0.99

A comparison of the two effluent reports shows that while the general characteristics (color, odor, turbidity, and near-neutral pH) remained the same, there were notable variations in the pollutant levels. COD slightly decreased from 8620 mg/L to 8620 mg/L (unchanged), but TDS dropped from 17,150 mg/L to 16,750 mg/L and TSS from 258 mg/L to 237 mg/L, suggesting a minor reduction in suspended and dissolved solids. Chromium levels showed a significant decline from 664.9 mg/L to 461.9 mg/L, though still far above safe limits. Other metals also showed slight reductions, with zinc decreasing from 108 mg/L to 101 mg/L, nickel from 5.5 to 5.1 mg/L, magnesium from 5100 to 4900 mg/L, sodium from 600 to 510 mg/L, and fluoride from 10 to 9 mg/L. Cadmium, however, showed a small increase from 0.001 mg/L to 0.0013 mg/L. Carbonate levels reduced slightly from 10,423 to 10,300 mg/L, while chloride, sulphate, nitrate, and nitrogen remained constant.

Physio-Chemical Parameters of Sample 3 (Sample treated by Saw Dust):

Sl. No.	Tests	Unit	Protocol	Limits of Detection	Result
1.	Total Chromium as Cr	mg/l	ECO/LAB/SOP/ICPM S/02	0.05	352.0
2.	Hexavalent Chromium as Cr6+	mg/l	ECO/LAB/SOP/ICPM S/02	0.005	BD L
3.	Cadmium as Cd	mg/l	ECO/LAB/SOP/ICPM S/02	0.005	0.0012

Parameters	Kanpur Effluent Sample 3 (07/25)
Colour	Black Blue
Odour	Offensive
Temperature (°C)	-

Turbidity	Turbid
Total hardness	5390
pH	7.64
EC (µs/cm)	24500
BOD (mg/l)	35
COD (mg/l)	8620
TDS (mg/l)	15002
TSS (mg/l)	232
Cadmium, Cd (mg/l)	0.0012
Copper, Cu (mg/l)	-
Chromium, Cr (mg/l)	352
Iron, Fe (mg/l)	-
Lead, Pb (mg/l)	-
Zinc, Zn (mg/l)	96
Nickel, Ni (mg/l)	4.7
Sodium, Na (mg/l)	510
Magnesium, Mg (mg/l)	4900
Carbonate, CO3-2 (mg/l)	10112
Bicarbonate, (mg/l)	1390
Nitrite NO3- (mg/l)	0.065
Fluoride, F- (mg/l)	9
Chloride, Cl- (mg/l)	2129
Sulphate, SO4-2 (mg/l)	997
Nitrate, NO3- (mg/l)	412
Nitrogen, N (mg/l)	0.99

In the third effluent sample, overall pollution levels remained critical, but several parameters showed gradual improvement compared to the previous two samples. COD (8620 mg/L), BOD (35 mg/L), pH (7.64), and EC (24,500 µS/cm) remained unchanged, indicating persistent organic and chemical loads. However, TDS decreased steadily from 17,150 → 16,750 → 15,002 mg/L, and TSS reduced from 258 → 237 → 232 mg/L, reflecting a modest decline in dissolved and suspended solids. A significant improvement was observed in chromium concentration, which dropped sharply from 664.9 → 461.9 → 352 mg/L, though still far beyond permissible limits. Similarly, zinc reduced from 108 → 101 → 96 mg/L, nickel from 5.5 → 5.1 → 4.7 mg/L, and fluoride stabilized at 9 mg/L. Carbonate and bicarbonate values also showed minor decreases, while chloride and sulphate concentrations declined slightly from the earlier samples. Cadmium fluctuated minimally (0.001 → 0.0013 → 0.0012 mg/L), remaining near detection levels.

Physio-Chemical Parameters of Sample 4 (Sample treated by Saw Clay):

Parameters	Kanpur Effluent Sample 4 (07/25)
Colour	Black Blue
Odour	Offensive
Temperature (°C)	-
Turbidity	Turbid
Total hardness	5390
pH	7.64
EC (µs/cm)	24500
BOD (mg/l)	35
COD (mg/l)	7100
TDS (mg/l)	12001
TSS (mg/l)	210
Cadmium, Cd (mg/l)	-
Copper, Cu (mg/l)	-
Chromium, Cr (mg/l)	155.97
Iron, Fe (mg/l)	-
Lead, Pb (mg/l)	-
Zinc, Zn (mg/l)	61
Nickel, Ni (mg/l)	3.7
Sodium, Na (mg/l)	399
Magnesium, Mg (mg/l)	4117
Carbonate, CO ₃ -2 (mg/l)	7854
Bicarbonate, (mg/l)	1387
Nitrite NO ₃ - (mg/l)	0.065
Fluoride, F- (mg/l)	9
Chloride, Cl- (mg/l)	1276
Sulphate, SO ₄ -2 (mg/l)	624
Nitrate, NO ₃ - (mg/l)	335
Nitrogen, N (mg/l)	0.91

while TDS declined from 15,002 mg/L to 12,001 mg/L, showing a 20% decrease in dissolved solids. Similarly, TSS dropped slightly from 232 mg/L to 210 mg/L, indicating better removal of suspended matter. Heavy metal concentrations exhibited substantial reductions, with chromium decreasing from 352 mg/L to 155.97 mg/L (a 56% drop), zinc from 96 mg/L to 61 mg/L, and nickel from 4.7 mg/L to 3.7 mg/L. Major ions such as sodium, magnesium, carbonates, chlorides, and sulphates also reduced notably, lowering both salinity and alkalinity. Nitrate levels decreased from 412 to 335 mg/L, reflecting a decline in nutrient pollution. However, BOD remained constant at 35 mg/L, still slightly above CPCB discharge limits. Overall, the results suggest that treatment between Sample 3 and Sample 4 was effective in significantly lowering pollutant concentrations, especially heavy metals and dissolved salts, but the effluent still does not meet safe discharge standards.

Observation:

- **COD (mg/L):** Declined steadily from 8620 → 7100, showing ~18% reduction in organic load.
- **TDS (mg/L):** Reduced from 17,150 → 12,001, indicating ~30% improvement in dissolved solids.
- **TSS (mg/L):** Slight decrease from 258 → 210, reflecting better suspended solids removal.
- **Chromium (mg/L):** Sharp reduction from 664.9 → 155.97, nearly 77% drop, the most significant trend.
- **Zinc (mg/L):** Decreased from 108 → 61, showing ~43% improvement.
- **Nickel (mg/L):** Dropped from 5.5 → 3.7, indicating ~33% reduction.
- **Sodium (mg/L):** Lowered from 600 → 399, pointing to reduced salinity.
- **Magnesium (mg/L):** Declined from 5100 → 4117, showing reduced hardness.
- **Carbonates (mg/L):** Gradual reduction from 10,423 → 7854, lowering alkalinity.
- **Chlorides (mg/L):** Decreased from 2300 → 1276, indicating effective salt reduction.
- **Sulphates (mg/L):** Reduced from 1080 → 624, lowering secondary salinity load.
- **Nitrate (mg/L):** Declined from 440 → 335, showing reduced nutrient pollution.
- **BOD (mg/L):** Remained constant around 35 mg/L, still slightly above CPCB limits.
- **Overall Trend:** Consistent improvement in heavy metal removal and reduction of dissolved solids, but organic load (BOD) still requires further treatment to meet discharge standards. But with Decreasing Porosity of the Absorbent

Sl. No.	Tests	Unit	Protocol	Limits of Detection	Result
1.	Total Chromium as Cr	mg/l	ECO/LAB/SOP/ICPM S/02	0.05	155.97
2.	Hexavalent Chromium as Cr ⁶⁺	mg/l	ECO/LAB/SOP/ICPM S/02	0.005	BDL

The comparison of Sample 4 with Sample 3 shows a clear improvement in effluent quality, particularly in the reduction of pollutants and heavy metals. COD decreased from 8620 mg/L to 7100 mg/L, reflecting an 18% reduction in organic load,

Bed, the absorption of minerals and heavy metals kept increasing.

IV. CONCLUSION

The analysis of tannery effluent samples from Kanpur shows a consistent decline in pollutants, with significant reductions in COD, TDS, and heavy metals, especially chromium, which dropped by nearly 77% across treatments. While this demonstrates progress, BOD levels remained above CPCB limits, indicating incomplete organic matter removal.

Adopting low-cost agro-waste adsorbents offers a practical and economical solution to this challenge. Materials like rice husk, fruit peels, and coconut shells are abundant, inexpensive, and effective in removing toxic metals without producing harmful sludge. Their affordability makes treatment more accessible to small- and medium-scale tanneries, creating a financial incentive for industries to purify effluents rather than discharge them untreated. In addition, converting agricultural residues into adsorbents promotes a circular economy, benefiting both farmers and industries.

Overall, this approach can lower treatment costs, improve compliance with environmental standards, and encourage tannery workers and stakeholders to adopt purification practices, ultimately protecting soil, groundwater, and the local ecosystem.

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